

Rewriting Patriarchy: A Feminist Reading of Grace Paley's “A Conversation with My Father”

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Abstract

This paper undertakes a feminist reading of Grace Paley’s “A Conversation with My Father”, positioning her work within the discourse of feminist theory as articulated by Hélène Cixous and Luce Irigaray. Engaging with the notion of “feminine writing” and the patriarchal underpinnings of language, this analysis reveals how Paley’s narrative techniques challenge fixed literary conventions and resist the rigidity of traditional storytelling. Through a fragmented and open-ended narrative structure, Paley subtly critiques her father’s demand for a typological and linear story, a preference that reflects the normative expectations of patriarchal literature. By foregrounding the body and privileging multiplicity, Paley echoes Cixous’ and Irigaray’s call for a new mode of representation, one that transcends the limits imposed by phallogocentric discourse. This paper explores how “A Conversation with My Father” serves as both an artistic and theoretical counterpoint to the masculine literary canon, advocating for a narrative form that embodies the fluidity, change, and diversity intrinsic to the feminine experience. In doing so, Paley’s work affirms the necessity of alternative voices in literature, voices that challenge the essentialist representations perpetuated by patriarchal modes of thinking.

Keywords: *Grace Paley, women’s writing, feminist reading, patriarchy, Hélène Cixous, Luce Irigaray.*

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Introduction

Women's Writing, as a distinct academic discipline, is based on the notion that gender has shaped the experience of women throughout history. Thus, this distinct branch of literary studies contends that women writers are worthy of separate study since their literary works are the product of peculiar conditions that are in general very different from those which characterize most (patriarchal) texts produced by men. It is mainly concerned with the position of women within the literary cannon. It also tries to read literary works through the lens of a ‘woman reader’ and asserts “continuity between women’s experience of social and familial structures and their experience as readers... [This] continuity takes considerable interest in the situations and psychology of female characters, investigating attitudes to women, or the “images of women” in the works of an author, a genre, or a period” (Culler, 1982, p. 46). Feminist figures, such as Hélène Cixous and Luce Irigaray, have tried to take the concept of a ‘woman reader’ a step further by advocating ‘feminine writing’ to go beyond phallogocentrism. They call for the invention of a completely new system of signification, a feminine mode of representation, which should operate through the body as they regard language and reason as patriarchal devices that oppress, subordinate and misrepresent women. This paper will try to extract the similar points and concepts between Cixous’ essay “The Laugh of the Medusa” and Irigaray’s “When Our Lips Speak Together”, and then deploy those similarities in reading Grace Paley’s “A Conversation with my Father”.

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Cixous' Medusa and the Subversion of Patriarchal Epistemology

To begin with, Cixous' essay's title is metaphorical. Medusa is a figure from Greek mythology, who is often considered a symbol of evil due to her deadly gaze and monstrous appearance. Originally a beautiful, golden-haired maiden, Medusa was punished by Athena after Poseidon took advantage of her in Athena's temple—a violation of her vow of chastity as a priestess. In her anger, Athena transformed Medusa into a Gorgon with snakes for hair and a gaze that would turn anyone who looked at her into stone (Greek Mythology). However, in Cixous' text, Medusa is invoked to oppose men and debunk the typical patriarchal reference to this mythical figure. Cixous deploys the Medusa to create a new perception based on the body. The body, in Cixous' terms, is a metaphor for creating alternative ways of thinking and new thoughts; women have been oppressed by patriarchal institutions, and they can only resist through writing that comes from the body. She writes: "Woman must write herself... Woman must put herself into the text—as into the world and into history—by her own movement. That is, writing and the body are one, and the text is reality (Cixous, 1976, p. 875). For her, women's writing should move beyond patriarchy to create a new epistemology.

Cixous contends that language is patriarchal. Therefore, reason is patriarchal as well since we think through language. She also criticizes psycho-analysis, of which a great deal is predicated on language and defines feminine sexuality in terms of binarism, while she conceives of it in terms of difference and multiplicity. She also favors difference over sameness. She argues that in order to understand sexuality, we have to understand language. Cixous refutes Freud's idea that there is one unconscious, one male and one female, and writes that "you can't talk about a female sexuality, uniform, homogeneous, classifiable into codes—any more than you can talk about one unconscious resembling another" (p. 876). She also deploys the unconscious, the imaginary in Lacan's terms, to criticize the symbolic, which is a territory dominated by patriarchy, wherein the male is 'self' and the female is 'other'. According to Lacan, the infant, in the imaginary phase, identifies as being part of the mother and conceives of the outside world as an extension of the mother. At this stage, everything is incongruous, ruleless and libidinal. Conversely, a successful move to the symbolic stage requires the repression of the unconscious. That is, all ties with the mother must be cut. Therefore, it signifies a passage into human subjectivity and rationality.

The multiplicity of female sexualities is the core of Cixous' non-theory theory. For her, the bisexual subject does not comprise of two entities (sexualities). It is a third body, in the sense of Bhabha's third-space. Moreover, she contends that women are more likely to be bisexual compared to men. She goes beyond Simone de Beauvoir who claims that the cultural influences the biological and argues that even the biological is cultural since it is language that makes one male or female. In this regard, she writes that "the future must no longer be determined by the past. I do not deny that the effects of the past are still with us. But I refuse to strengthen them by repeating them, to confer upon them an irremovability the equivalent of destiny, to confuse the biological and the cultural" (p. 875). She asserts that the aforementioned 'third-body' results in a multiplicity of subjectivities in one self. Thus, the term 'woman' is not homogeneous; it refers to a multitude of selves: poor, rich, young, old, etc. Cixous uses strategic essentialism to dismantle the essentialist patriarchal representations of women. However, her essay is only the inception of a feminist theory, hence the naming non-theory theory. It is still at the first stages of theorizing women's position in society and the world of literature and draws on post-structural and postmodern thought in its open-endedness and incessant process of revision.

Irigaray's Vision of Language and Identity beyond Patriarchy

In the same fashion, Luce Irigaray, in her essay "When Our Lips Speak Together", contends that language, as a system of signification, is patriarchal as it violates the very existence of women, as independent selves with their own peculiar identity. She explains that women's identity is negotiated in terms of the proper names given to them by patriarchal institutions: the father, husband, etc. She writes: "If we continue to speak this sameness, if we speak to each other as men have spoken for centuries, as they taught us to speak, we will fail each other [...] We have fled into proper names, we have been violated

by them. Not yours, not mine. We don't have names. We change them as men exchange us, as they use us” (Irigaray, 1980, p. 69).

She also defines female sexuality in terms of multiplicity and difference and argues that women’s identity is not homogenous and fixed but open-ended and perpetually in process. She makes use of the body to materialize this open-endedness. She writes “We–you/I–are never open nor closed. [...] From your/my lips, several songs, several ways of saying echo each other. For one is never separable from the other. You/I are always several at the same time” (72). Furthermore, Irigaray, like Cixous, denies the biological as she explains that it is solely cultural by writing: “That our lips make us women does not mean that consuming, consummating, or being filled is what matters to us” (73). She adds that a woman’s body “does not acquire a sex by some operation, by the act of some power, function, or organ” (74). Moreover, she protests the patriarchal binaries virgin/non-virgin, pure/impure, innocent/knowing as names and choices imposed on women. Then, she urges women to speak their multiplicity out, even though they were not taught nor allowed to do so as “that would have been improper speech” (73).

Irigaray postulates that women do not need to be defined in terms of patriarchal representations, for a woman is already a woman regardless of “any special modification or intervention” (74). Also she criticizes Lacan for conceiving of women as *‘pas toutes’* (not whole). According to Irigaray, women can achieve ‘wholeness’ through the body:

This "all" can't be schematized or mastered. It's the total movement of our body. No surface holds: no figures, lines, and points; no ground subsists. But there is no abyss. For us, depth does not mean a chasm. Where the earth has no solid crust, there can be no precipice. Our depth is the density of our body, in touch "all" over. There is no above/below, back/front, right side/wrong side, top/bottom in isolation, separate, out of touch. Our "all" intermingles. Without breaks or gaps. (75)

Equally important, she advocates speaking and writing through the body, just like Cixous, because it grants women the ability to voice out their differences and multiple standpoints shamelessly and without restrictions and boundaries that the patriarchal modes of representation are predicated on. In this regard, she writes: “Don't fret about the "right" word. There is none. No truth between our lips. Everything has the right to be. Everything is worth exchanging, without privileges or refusals” (76). Irigaray expresses the need to invent an open-ended system of signification that will help women pull themselves out of the fixity, subordination and oppression of patriarchal modes of thinking because women “are made for endless change” (76). She explains this idea as follows:

If we don't invent a language, if we don't find our body's language, its gestures will be too few to accompany our story. When we become tired of the same ones, we'll keep our desires secret, unrealized. Asleep again, dissatisfied, we will be turned over to the words of men. (76)

She states that this language is going to keep all women connected together anytime and anywhere. And she expresses hope and optimism when she states that “one day we will learn to say ourselves. And what we say will be far more beautiful than our tears, totally fluent” (77). In addition, Irigaray writes that “if I say again and again: not, nor, without ..., it's to remind you, to remind us, that we can touch each other only when naked. And that to find ourselves and each other, we have a great deal to take off.

Paley’s Feminist and Postmodern Response to Patriarchal Storytelling

As shown above, Hélène Cixous and Luce Irigaray contest patriarchy and language as a patriarchal system. In like manner, Grace Paley ironically criticizes the dying institution of patriarchy which is symbolized by her old and sick father. The use of the first pronoun “my” signifies that she is, as a woman, writing for all women and gives more ground to the feminist subject. She implicitly criticizes psychoanalysis which defines the father as the law, yet hers is very old and dying. She makes this point clear through her humorous repetition of the word “old”, as an adjective and a noun. She does not take patriarchal authority

seriously; she is playful like Cixous who symbolically uses the laughter of the Medusa as a critique of patriarchal order and Irigaray who ridicules it.

Furthermore, Paley criticizes rationality, which is the basis of all Western epistemology. She writes “my father is eighty-six years old and in bed. His heart, that bloody motor, is equally old and will not do certain jobs anymore. It still floods his head with brainy light”. She describes the father as being physically disabled—he is dying, yet he still relies on reason and ridiculously gives rational explanations of his physical decline: “despite my metaphors, this muscle failure is not due to his old heart, he says, but to a potassium shortage”. Paley, like Cixous and Irigaray, privileges the body over the mind. This is an open critique to patriarchy.

Paley brings up the names of famous authors such as Maupassant, Chekhov and Turgenev, who represent different literary movements like naturalism, realism and modernism, to criticize literature for being typological, and thus patriarchal. Her father wants her to follow the lead of such patriarchal figures and write according to their fixed generic norms which make a good story (linear plots), according to him. However, it can be seen that Paley is a postmodernist writer since her story is open-ended and fragmented. She also uses other important postmodern techniques of writing such as meta-fiction (a story within a story) and parody.

Paley states that “everyone, real or invented, deserves the open destiny of life”. This is a call to blur the rift between reality and fiction; this is a characteristic of postmodern literature. For Paley, writing stories is writing about different humans and about their diverse experiences. She refuses linear plots and generic characters; instead she advocates open-ended stories and expresses hope and optimism, like Cixous and Irigaray, as she believes in change. Similarly, Irigaray writes: “Be what you are becoming, without clinging to what you could have been, might be” (p. 76).

In the story Paley’s narrator writes for her father, we have a mother and her junkie son indulging in drugs. This is a reference to the indulgence in the body. In Cixous’ terms, the mother and her son are writing their bodies. It is through hallucinogenic drugs that the mother succeeds to connect with her son. It is through the body. It is also through her bodily relation with her son that the mother succeeds at finding a job at a clinic and re-establishing a decent life, even though the father would have concluded her story tragically since he does not believe in change. It can also be seen that Paley identifies with this mother bodily. Cixous and Irigaray also call for the invention of an open-ended language that connects women through the body and help them embrace each other anytime and anywhere. Likewise, Paley’s short story is an attempt to rewrite, revise and renew literature through the lens of a woman.

Conclusion

In the final analysis, Hélène Cixous, Luce Irigaray, and Grace Paley illuminate the pervasive impact of patriarchal structures on women's identities, experiences, and voices, revealing how language and reason have historically been used as instruments of oppression, subjugation, and misrepresentation. They critique these tools not merely as linguistic or intellectual devices but as extensions of a patriarchal system that has long marginalized women by confining them to restrictive roles and definitions. In response, they advocate for an alternative system of meaning-making—an open-ended system of signification rooted in the body. Here, the body becomes a powerful metaphor and site of resistance, representing a means of expression and knowledge that defies traditional logic and challenges the restrictive frameworks of Western philosophy.

Cixous, Irigaray, and Paley reimagine the body as a source of knowledge, creativity, and connection, proposing a mode of understanding that transcends the binaries and hierarchies upon which patriarchal discourse is built. In doing so, they envision a “feminine epistemology” that is fluid, relational, and capable of fostering unity among women, empowering them to reclaim their experiences and identities on their own terms. By privileging the body over the mind—an approach that counters Western

philosophy's historic focus on rationality as the highest form of knowledge—they introduce a pathway toward a collective, embodied sense of wholeness among women.

Their work calls for a radical shift from the fixed, binary, and essentialist representations of women to an inclusive, dynamic conception of identity characterized by multiplicity, openness, and difference. Through their writing, they lay the groundwork for a transformative feminist epistemology that celebrates diversity within womanhood and resists rigid categorizations. This vision not only seeks to disrupt patriarchal narratives but also aspires to create a literary and philosophical space where women can articulate their experiences in ways that honor their complexity and fluidity. Ultimately, Cixous, Irigaray, and Paley urge for a literary and intellectual revolution—one that dismantles existing constraints and opens up possibilities for women to express and understand themselves beyond patriarchal limitations.

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